

GLASSY CARBON PARTICLES AS A REINFORCEMENT OF MAGNESIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The glassy carbon (GC) called also amorphous carbon is well known material because of its mechanical properties and first of all thermal and chemical stability. Composite materials can be another field of glassy carbon application, but in form of particles with variable granulation or as a matrix. Therefore glassy carbon particles were particularly proposed for tribiological applications [1] in composites with polymer and aluminium matrix. In the present paper an application of glassy carbon particles in magnesium matrix composite is reported [2,3].

2 Characteristic of Glassy Carbon Particles

2.1 Manufacturing

Glassy carbon particles (GC_p) were manufactured according to the following recipe: a) polymerization of an organic resin, b) pyrolysis of organic precursor into GC, c) milling of GC, c) sieving of GC to proper fractions. Results of applied technological steps were presented at Figs 1-3.

2.2 Microstructure and Properties

Examination of GC_p by X-ray diffraction method (XRD) confirmed their amorphous structure and observation by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showed they characteristic irregular shape with sharp edges (Fig. 3). Their microhardness was estimated as ~260HV. Our own experiments showed that GC_p can be applied "as obtained" or surface modified with TiC or HfC nanolayers formed by reactive chemical vapor deposition method (RCVD),

with nanolayer of TiN deposited by chemical vapor deposition method (CVD) as well as with SiO₂ nanolayer obtained by sol-gel method.

3 Magnesium Matrix Composite with Glassy Carbon Particles

3.1 Composite Microstructure

Composite samples were obtained from homogenous mixture of glassy carbon particles and pure magnesium or its alloys of variable composition. The consolidation process is in progress by wetting of solid state particles with liquid matrix. Independently on magnesium alloy composition the microstructure investigations shown the uniform distribution of particles and their good cohesion with a matrix (Fig.4).

3.2 Interface Microstructure

Because of fundamental role of reinforcement-matrix interface properties its microstructure was investigated with SEM and TEM methods. It was found that during the wetting of glassy carbon and further cooling of the system the new phases (Fig.5) were formed with composition dependent of applied GC_p surface modification and magnesium matrix chemical composition. The effect of oxygen originally absorbed by carbon material and its reactions with metallic elements of magnesium matrix were always observed.

4 Summary

Results of laboratory and industrial experiments showed that glassy carbon can be applied in form of particles with variable granulation as a reinforcement of magnesium based composites. Properly selected technological parameters of the composite manufacturing ensured good wettability

of GC_p by liquid matrix and the reactive bonding between components.

Fig.1. Macrostructure of GC organic precursor.

Fig.2. Macrostructure of GC before milling process.

Fig.3. Microstructure (SEM) of GC particles applied in experiments.

Fig.4. Microstructure (SEM) of magnesium matrix composite reinforced with GC particles.

Fig.5. Microstructure (SEM) of bonding formed between GC (left) and magnesium matrix (right).

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